

EUROPRACTICE's pan-European platform makes design tools accessible and fuels ATP breakthroughs

Best practice category	ATP in Europe and New impetus for chip design
Stakeholder group	Associations, trade organisations and consortia
Value chain position	Fabrications

General Information

The EUROPRACTICE platform is a pan-European chip infrastructure for design innovation composed of five partners (Imec, UKRI-STFC, Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft, CIME-P and Tyndall National Institute) that provides European industry and academia with a platform to develop electronic circuits and systems. It was set up by the European Commission in 1995 to enhance European industrial competitiveness in the global market. The platform is used by more than 600 European academic and research institutions and 300 European SMEs.

Annually, EUROPRACTICE delivers 65,000 concurrent licences of design tool flows to European universities and research centres, more than 800 fabricated prototypes for European academic and industrial customers and provides training to more than 500 engineers. It has been in operation since it was launched in 1995 by the European Commission to enhance European industrial competitiveness in the global market.

Activities and best practices

EUROPRACTICE lowers the barriers to entry for industry and academia seeking access to electronic smart systems technologies by making them more affordable and accessible. This occurs thanks to a coordinated brokerage service, which offers pre-negotiated prices and extensive customer support and stimulation of the tools.

Thus, the customers get access to a wide range of CAD tools, training courses and state-of-the-art fabrication technologies, including ASICs, MEMS, photonics and microfluidics; EUROPRACTICE partners offer their expertise and support from prototype design all the way to volume production. The customers can use these advanced microelectronic technologies to innovate and exploit them in different application domains, all within the scope of their non-commercial research. Below, some highlights from how EUROPRACTICE enables the access to packaging and design tools in Europe.

- For ASIC packaging, EUROPRACTICE boosts the deployment of its clients' chip backend operations through standard and custom packaging. It provides clear package design rules and pricing lists for ceramic and open-pak packages, covering (ceramic) small outline ICs, leadless and leaded chip carriers, among others. Customers can order a minimum of 10 (Fraunhofer, Imec) or 5 packages (CMP), in addition to requesting customised assembly for novel applications not covered in the basic listing.

- Tyndall is the EUROPRACTICE partner responsible for photonics packaging. Similarly to ASIC packaging, this is offered for competitive prices, and a choice of either fibre-only coupling or fully packaged modules. Tyndall also released package design rules and a handbook on packaging and integration services.
- The group also offers services in system and chiplet integration for customers interested in combining packages/devices. This mix-and-match approach leads to higher yields and reduced development times and costs, potentially unlocking more uses and applications in fields like telecommunications and biomedicine.
- Once customers are ready to move to low- and medium-volume production, EUROPRACTICE offers them five-step testing services in the form of test insertion and ATPG. Based on their expertise, the partners offer their know-how to improve the design for testability (DFT) techniques, produce prototypes, develop qualification procedures and move the test boards into production. They also deploy multi layer mask techniques to reduce production costs.

The consortium hosts training courses and webinars for academic staff and students who are Academic and Research Laboratory Members of EUROPRACTICE and are interested to know more about the supported CAD tools and technologies. This knowledge transfer enables greater collaboration and enables European research and academic institutions to stay up to date on the latest developments.

Challenges addressed with this practice

One of the significant challenges in the semiconductor industry is access to cutting-edge technologies and tools, especially for smaller companies and academic institutions. EUROPRACTICE's brokerage and training services help to bridge the gap between global industry players and European research and academic institutes, promoting innovation. Furthermore, this access to shared resources, expertise, and knowledge addresses the challenge of siloed development and encourages a more interconnected semiconductor ecosystem. Its assistance in prototyping and testing, enables a smoother transition from design to production, all with reduced costs and optimised production and testing processes.